

Homestays as Engines of Rural Development: Evidence from Darap Village, Sikkim

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the socio-economic factors influencing the monthly profit of homestay operators in Darap, a prominent eco-tourism village in West Sikkim. Based on primary data collected from 42 homestay operators and analyzed using a multiple linear regression model, the results reveal that the operators' experience and the number of tourist groups hosted have a statistically significant and positive impact on monthly profit. In contrast, total operating cost shows a negative and moderately significant relationship with profit, indicating the importance of cost efficiency. Other variables such as age, education level, and investment were found to be statistically insignificant in determining profitability. The model explains approximately 79.7% of the variation in monthly profit, confirming its robustness and relevance. The findings underscore the critical role of operational experience and guest flow in enhancing the financial viability of homestays, while highlighting the challenges posed by increasing operational costs. These insights can aid policymakers in designing targeted support mechanisms and capacity-building programs to strengthen rural tourism and livelihood opportunities in Sikkim.

Keywords: Socioeconomic, Homestays, Ecotourism, Sikkim, profitability, livelihood

INTRODUCTION

Tourism refers to those traveling for less than a year for leisure, business, or other reasons (UNWTO, 2019). It is a significant contributor to the global economy (Dwyer et al., 2020) and one of the world's fastest-growing industries (Riddhagni and Taylor, 2019). In 2019, the travel

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and tourism industry accounted for 10.3% of global GDP, or nearly \$8.9 trillion. In recent years, the tourism and hospitality industries have taken on critical socioeconomic functions (Konovalova et al., 2018), providing benefits such as job creation, investment opportunities, lodging services, cultural and natural attractions, festivals, recreational activities, higher living standards, and overall regional development.

The World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) have named India as one of the fastest-growing tourism industries for the next 10 to 15 years. The Indian tourism industry has outperformed the global tourism industry in terms of growth in the volume of international tourists as well as in terms of revenue. Tourism in India is not only at an all-time high but is growing faster than in any other region (Yassin et al., 2010). India has uniqueness in cultural and natural information and is known for its best hospitality.

Under the Ministry of Tourism, Government of India, states like Kerala, Karnataka, Himachal Pradesh, New Delhi, Goa, Uttarakhand, Sikkim, Rajasthan, and Gujarat have adopted the concept of Homestays and formulated policies for operating homestays in tourist destinations. The policy of the homestay could be experience-based, socially responsible, home hospitality, eco-friendly, and hotel comfort. The main product varieties offered by the homestay are accommodations, cuisines, amenities, local activities, and sightseeing.

There is a popular saying in India that, a guest is equivalent to God. As a multilingual and multicultural country, India has a long history of welcoming and serving guests from within and outside the country (Andrade et al., 2017). The government of India through the '*Atithi Devo Bhava*' campaign has given crucial importance to providing inbound tourists a greater sense of being welcomed to the country. In the modern era of globalization, the tourism industry is considered a rapidly growing industry in India, especially in the North Eastern states of India (Acharya, 2013).

Tourism has emerged as an important sector in the North Eastern region due to its physical and geographical variety of human resources and there is a need for the adoption of a sustainable tourism development strategy (Rizal & Asokan, 2013). Six to seven percent of tourists from Britain and Australia visit northeastern tourist spots for nostalgic attraction (Bhattacharya, 2008). Tourism have been a major source of revenue generation and economic growth in the North Eastern (N.E) region. Different types of tourism exist in the N.E region: adventure tourism, eco-tourism, business tourism, etc. (Scutariu, et al., 2016). The tourism industry has strong relevance to economic development, cultural growth, and national integration. The

tourism industry has helped growth even in other sectors as diverse as horticulture, handicrafts, agriculture, and construction (Ribeiro et al., 2017).

Sikkim, a part of the Eastern Himalaya, is known for its rich biodiversity and diverse climates, ranging from alpine to subtropical. It is also home to Kanchenjunga, the highest peak in India and the third highest on Earth. The capital of Sikkim is Gangtok, which is its primate city. Kanchenjunga National Park covers almost 35% of the state. The World Tourism Organization defines visitors as 'any person travelling to a place other than that of his/her usual environment for less than 12 months and whose main purpose of the trip is other than the exercise of an activity remunerated from within the place visited' (UN/WTO 2002-03).

Sikkim being a sub-state holds a dominant place due to its Tourism with the blend of different cultures. The natural beauties of Sikkim make it an important tourist destination for tourists. Its rapid growth and development have contributed to the socio-economic development of the state. Tourism has become a major source of employment and income generation in Sikkim. The government has accorded tourism as a priority sector to bring economic and social development to Sikkim (Government of Sikkim, 2012).

Sikkim's natural beauty and rich cultural heritage have been attracting a large number of tourists to the state. Tourism in Sikkim is growing rapidly in a well-planned manner. The state has become one of the most sought-after hill destinations globally. The government is committed and effective in educating and guiding the people about tourism, focusing on the principle of Sustainable Development. Strong measures have been taken to preserve the state's culture, traditions, heritage, and environment. Well-planned programs and policies by the state and central government are being implemented to enhance tourism and provide education to the youth and other stakeholders involved in the tourism sector. The policy aims to prioritize tourism as the primary civil industry in the state, creating employment opportunities and fostering economic integration by developing linkages with other sectors.

The home stays under the UNESCO project include Yuksam Home Stays, Kewzing Home Stays, Hee-Bermiok Home Stays, Lachen Home Stays, and Seven Hills Resort. These home stays are managed by the Tourism Development Committee at the local level, with marketing activities overseen by the Department of Tourism, Government of Sikkim. Initially, home stay programs were introduced in remote tourism areas where there was no hotel or lodging facilities available (Sanyal et al., 2023). A home stay provides an alternative food and accommodation arrangement by the host in a tourist destination.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Nilson (2006), ecotourism in India is ecologically and economically sustainable nature and culture tourism, where he found that Ecotourism contributes direct money to the local rural economy. Similar findings have been found by Tambe et al., (2007) in India, ecotourism transforming rural villages into model villages as well as it has contributed to reviving cultural values and providing a means of livelihood.

The socioeconomic status of people has improved after they got involved in ecotourism services revealed by (Kumari & Kumar 2015). Cotthem (2007) in Africa viewed Ecotourism, as a new source of income that transforms rural communities into urban ones. Similar findings related to rural development, sustainable development, social improvement, and development of social attitude through ecotourism were also reported in Romania by (Dorobantu & Nistoreanu, 2012).

Sikkim is known as the home of Mt. Kanchendzonga, the third highest mountain in the world, land of elaborate festivals and fairs, snow-capped mountains, lakes, religious hubs, hot springs, diverse cultures and natural wonders. This creates a refreshing atmosphere that promotes ecotourism in Sikkim where, ecotourism has been improving both the social and economic status of people (Bhattarai, 2015). Similarly, Chandel et al., (2024) mentioned that ecotourism in Sikkim has a direct impact on local communities by contributing to their main source of income.

Chakraborty and Ghoshal (2022) in India also found that the homestay is successful in promoting and enriching the upliftment of the cultural tourism business through exploration and discussion of homestay and cultural tourism. Similarly, Hussin (2018) in Malaysia described that participation in the homestay program could offer the villagers economic benefits such as job opportunities, improved family income, and an improved standard of living.

Despite the growing popularity of homestays and ecotourism as an alternative form of accommodation and sustainable tourism practices, there remains a notable gap in the literature regarding the role played by homestays and the socio-economic implications of homestays on local communities, particularly in the context of Darap, West Sikkim. While existing studies have explored the economic impact of tourism in various destinations, there is a lack of in-depth analysis focusing especially on the socio-economic development of homestay owners in Darap. Moreover, there are very few studies that have systematically examined sustainable

tourism in Darap, and none of them has examined the challenges faced by homestay owners. Addressing this research gap is crucial for developing a comprehensive understanding of the socio-economic dynamics of homestays in Darap and for informing sustainable tourism policies and practices in the region.

DATABASE AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study is conducted in Darap village, located in the Gyalshing district of West Sikkim, a region that has emerged as a prominent hub for eco-cultural tourism. Darap was purposively selected due to its significant concentration of homestays and its comparative advantage in attracting tourists over other villages in the region. The study adopts a mixed-methods approach, relying on both quantitative and qualitative techniques. Primary data were collected from 42 homestay operators using a pre-structured questionnaire and personal interviews, selected through a random sampling technique. These data were aimed at understanding the socio-economic profile of operators, the nature of their engagement with ecotourism, and the challenges they face. Secondary data were obtained from government reports, academic journals, books, and relevant online sources. Descriptive statistics such as means, frequencies, tables, and charts were used to summarize the data. Furthermore, a multiple linear regression model was employed to analyse the impact of various socio-economic factors on monthly profits (MP) from homestay operations. The model includes explanatory variables such as age (AGE), education (EDU), number of tourist groups hosted (GH), investment made (INV), total cost of operation (TC), and experience in homestay business (EXP), allowing for a robust assessment of profitability determinants in the rural tourism context of Sikkim which can be specified as;

$$MP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1(AGE)_i + \beta_2(EDU)_i + \beta_3(GH)_i + \beta_4(INV)_i + \beta_5(TC)_i + \beta_6(EXP)_i + \epsilon_i$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The table 1 provides a detailed socio-demographic breakdown of the 42 homestay operators surveyed in Darap village. The gender distribution reveals a significant male dominance in homestay operations, with 85.71% of respondents being male and only 14.29% female. This suggests that while women may participate in managing homestays informally, formal ownership or registration is primarily male-dominated.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Homestay Operators

Particulars	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	36	85.71
Female	6	14.29
Age (Years)		
Below 25	0	0.00
26-45	32	76.19
46-65	10	23.80
Above 65	0	0.00
Category		
ST	35	83.33
SC	1	2.38
OBC	1	2.38
MBC	5	11.90
Religion		
Hindu	28	66.67
Christian	6	14.29
Buddhist	8	19.05
Family Size		
1-3	16	38.09
4-6	24	57.14
Above 7	2	4.76

Source: Field Survey

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In terms of age, the majority (76.19%) of operators fall within the 26–45 years range, indicating that the business is largely managed by individuals in their economically productive years. The remaining 23.80% are between 46 and 65 years, while there are no operators under 25 or above 65, highlighting a lack of involvement from both younger and older age groups.

The social category of respondents shows a high representation of Scheduled Tribes (ST), who constitute 83.33% of the sample. Minor representation is observed from the Most Backward Classes (MBC) at 11.90%, and both Scheduled Castes (SC) and Other Backward Classes (OBC) at 2.38% each. This indicates that the homestay business in Darap is primarily rooted in tribal communities, reflecting the region's ethnic composition.

Regarding religion, the majority of homestay operators identify as Hindu (66.67%), followed by Buddhists (19.05%) and Christians (14.29%). This reflects the religious diversity of the area while showing a Hindu majority among business owners.

The family size distribution reveals that most households are medium-sized, with 57.14% having 4–6 members. Smaller families (1–3 members) make up 38.09%, and only a small fraction (4.76%) report large families with more than 7 members. This suggests a manageable family structure that may support homestay operations through family labor while keeping household expenditure in check.

Overall, the table highlights that homestay enterprises in Darap are primarily male-led, managed by middle-aged individuals from tribal backgrounds, with most operators belonging to Hindu households and medium-sized families. These socio-demographic patterns provide insights into the structure and inclusivity of the local tourism economy.

The regression analysis presented in Table 2 identifies the key socio-economic factors influencing the monthly profit of homestay operators in Darap, West Sikkim. The model demonstrates a strong explanatory power, with an R-square value of 0.7971, indicating that approximately 79.7% of the variation in monthly profit is explained by the included variables. The F-value of 22.92 is highly significant ($p < 0.01$), confirming the overall robustness of the model.

Table 2: Factors influencing monthly profit of Homestay Operators in Darap

Variables	coefficients	z	p-value
<i>Dependent Variable:</i>			
<i>Monthly Profit of Homestays Operators</i>			
Intercept	-37941.1	-0.48	0.632
Age	-804.985	-0.63	0.530
Education	-1697.68	-0.41	0.682
Experience	25985.99	3.22	0.002***
Groups hosted	10480.15	5.34	0.000***
Investment	0.025781	1.57	0.123
Total Cost	-0.53958	-1.83	0.075*
R-square	0.7971		
F-Value	22.92		0.000***
No. of observations	42		

Note: *, ** and *** indicates the significance levels at 10%, 5% and 1% respectively.

Source: Field Survey

Among the independent variables, experience and number of groups hosted are statistically significant at the 1% level and exhibit a strong positive relationship with monthly profit. Specifically, each additional year of experience in managing a homestay is associated with an increase of approximately ₹25,986 in monthly profit, while hosting one additional tourist group increases profit by about ₹10,480. These findings underscore the importance of accumulated experience and higher tourist inflow in enhancing profitability.

On the other hand, total cost is negatively associated with monthly profit and is statistically significant at the 10% level. This suggests that an increase in operating costs slightly reduces profits, highlighting the need for cost-effective management. The coefficients for age, education, and investment are not statistically significant, indicating that these variables do not have a direct or substantial influence on profit within this sample. Notably, investment shows a positive but insignificant effect, which may suggest that merely investing more does not guarantee higher profits without efficient management or sufficient tourist flow.

In summary, the analysis reveals that practical experience and the ability to attract more tourist groups are critical drivers of profit for homestay operators, while rising operational costs can pose challenges. These insights can inform targeted training and support programs for improving the financial sustainability of homestays in rural tourism settings like Darap.

CONCLUSION

This study explored the role of homestays and eco-tourism in enhancing the socio-economic development of Darap village, West Sikkim. Using both descriptive statistics and a multiple linear regression model, the research found that homestays significantly contribute to income generation, employment creation, and local business development. The empirical results revealed that the operators' experience and the number of tourist groups hosted are the key drivers of monthly profit. While investment and education were not statistically significant, rising operational costs were found to negatively affect profitability. The study confirms that homestay-based tourism has become a vital livelihood option for rural communities in Sikkim, especially among Scheduled Tribe populations.

Based on the findings, two key policy recommendations are proposed to enhance the sustainability and profitability of homestay operations in Darap. First, targeted skill development and capacity-building programs should be introduced to equip homestay operators—especially new entrants—with essential knowledge in hospitality management, digital marketing, and customer service. These programs can be facilitated through local

tourism departments or NGOs and would help improve service quality and tourist satisfaction, ultimately boosting earnings.

Second, there is a pressing need to improve access to affordable finance for homestay operators. Government-backed low-interest loan schemes or subsidies for infrastructure development and maintenance can ease the financial burden, particularly for small operators. Facilitating easier access to credit will enable them to invest in quality facilities, attract more tourists, and increase profitability. These two interventions can significantly strengthen rural tourism and livelihood opportunities in regions like Darap.

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